

**INTERPRETATION OF FEMALE IMAGES IN D. RUDINA'S NOVEL "ON THE
SUNNY SIDE OF THE STREET" BY THE EXAMPLE OF THE HEROINES KATYA
AND VERA SHCHEGLOVA**

Обидова Фарангиз Акмаловна

Термезский государственный университет,

г. Термез, Узбекистан.

E-mail: bafada.0407@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11115760>

Abstract. *The article analyzes female images using the example of the novel "On the Sunny Side of the Street" by Dina Rudina. both heroines have their own individual character traits, and each of them has their own unique life path. Despite their differences in their approaches to life and strategies for achieving their goals, both women strive to find their place in the world and achieve happiness and fulfillment.*

Key words: *female images, character, art, gallery, artist, faith, mother.*

**ИНТЕРПРЕТАЦИЯ ЖЕНСКИХ ОБРАЗОВ В РОМАНЕ Д. РУДИНА «НА
СОЛНЕЧНОЙ СТОРОНЕ УЛИЦЫ» НА ПРИМЕРЕ ГЕРОИНЬ КАТИ И ВЕРЫ
ЩЕГЛОВЫХ**

Аннотация. *В статье анализируются женские образы на примере романа Дины Рудиной «На солнечной стороне улицы». обе героини обладают своими индивидуальными чертами характера, и у каждой из них свой неповторимый жизненный путь. Несмотря на различия в подходах к жизни и стратегиях достижения своих целей, обе женщины стремятся найти свое место в мире и достичь счастья и самореализации.*

Ключевые слова: *женские образы, персонаж, искусство, галерея, художница, вера, мать.*

Dina Rubina is a Russian writer, editor and screenwriter. Born in Tashkent, her works are often imbued with images of this city and the realities of the author's past, as well as elements of Uzbek culture. For example, in the story "Lyubka", the main character was born in Tashkent, worked in a provincial corner, and then returned to her hometown, which reminds of her connection with this place. In addition, Lubka buys slippers with Uzbek patterns from an old man for a symbolic price, which is just one of the many aspects of Uzbek themes present in the work of Dina Rubina. Of particular importance in the literary legacy of Dina Rubina is the novel "On the sunny side of the Street", on which the writer worked for 26 years. In an interview, the author

admitted: "Writing a novel is a long and time-consuming process, especially when it comes to recreating images of her hometown." The novel "On the sunny side of the street" takes place in the city of Tashkent. In this work, the author recalls his hometown, the place of his childhood, although this city itself no longer exists. She describes life in Tashkent in the post-war years, the period of evacuation during the war. The image of Tashkent in the novel attracts the attention of researchers and young scientists. The author gives accurate descriptions of the old streets, squares and bazaars of the city, as well as its life. In the novel, there are two parallel storylines associated with the main characters: Katya Shcheglova and her daughter Vera. Through Katya's memories, we learn about her past: she survived the Leningrad blockade as a child, her only surviving relative was her brother Sasha, who died after the war, leaving her alone. Katya was a talented girl, studied languages, and spoke French, but the difficulties that accompanied her life led to the fact that she aspired to a better life and "despised all effort." Her desire for material gain came from childhood traumas and losses that shaped her character. The main character of the novel, Katka, appears to the reader as a woman with a sharp, rude character, she has outstanding cunning and strives for power in relationships with others. More often than not, she herself never obeys others. However, watching the young Katya, Seven Fingers feels surprised: it seems to him that she is attractively unexpected.

In her sharp and changeable character, sometimes softened and clarified in warm moments of emotional communication, he sees a resemblance to a restorer who carefully removes the covering of time to expose the beauty of the true image beneath him, revealing a piece of sky above the roof of the house and a light cloud previously unnoticed. These swings from tenderness to aggression tickled and worried Seven Fingers. Katya, a highly gifted woman, did not accidentally receive the nickname "artist" among her like-minded people. She could masterfully pretend and transform, which helped her in seducing and gaining the trust of other people in order to carry out her brilliant plans. The complete opposite of Katya Shcheglova is her daughter Vera.

She is also independent and strong, but for Vera, the main values are not money, but love, beauty and harmony. After the mother, Katya, returns from prison, the relationship between her and her daughter, Vera, can be filled with a variety of emotions and dynamics. Perhaps Vera has mixed feelings about her mother. On the one hand, she may feel relief from the release of her mother and joy at the possibility of reconnecting with her. On the other hand, she may be cautious or fearful of her mother's return to their lives due to previous difficult relationships or past mistakes. Vera may also feel compassion or pity for her mother because she went to prison, and try to support her during this difficult period. At the same time, she may feel disappointed or annoyed about the situation that led to her mother being imprisoned. In general, these relationships can be complex and their development depends on many factors, including the personal characters

and life circumstances of the heroines. The daughter's hatred of her own mother, Katya, may be due to a series of traumatic events from her childhood that shaped her relationship with her mother and left a deep mark on her psyche. Vera often felt lost and lonely as a child because her mother forgot her in various places or went away to "earn money." She felt fear and anxiety from this instability and lack of protection. These situations left her with deep wounds and caused feelings of helplessness and resentment. The episode when the mother rejects Fedya's offer to marry him shows Katya's cold and indifferent attitude towards her daughter, as well as her lack of maternal love and care. This confirms that Vera felt unwanted and rejected by her mother, which could contribute to the development of hatred and negative emotions towards her in the future. Thus, Vera's hatred of her mother may be the result of accumulated negative experiences and feelings of inferiority that she experienced in her childhood due to her mother's indifference and negligence.

For Katya, the "sunny side of the street" can symbolize her memories of a bright and carefree childhood, of the simplicity and warmth she experienced in her early years. While for Vera, who grew up in a darker and more complex environment, the "sunny side of the street" is a meeting with people who bring light and joy into her life, create her world bright and saturated.

Although Katya and Vera's paths are different, they both strive for their own happiness and the fulfillment of their dreams, and their stories serve as a reminder that each person has their own path to happiness and wholeness.

REFERENCES

1. Rubina D. *On the sunny side of the street*. Moscow 2006. P. 360
2. Babaeva, A. A. The image of the author in Dina Rubina's novel "On the Sunny Side of the Street" / A. A. Babaeva. — Text: immediate // *Young scientist*. - 2016. - No. 3 (107). - pp. 1067-1069. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/107/25698/>
3. Alekseeva N.V.«ON THE SUNNY SIDE OF THE STREET» BY D. RUBINA: the social and cultural phenomenon of the City born by "the winds of historic upheavals". *Political linguistics*-2015.